

3D Room Generation

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Abstract

The advent of Large Language Models (LLMs) has ushered in a new era of creative content generation and artificial intelligence applications. In this research, we present a 3D scene generation framework that harnesses the power of LLMs to reshape the process of creating immersive virtual environments. This framework seamlessly transforms basic textual descriptions into visually coherent and realistic 3D scenes through LLMs, providing users with an intuitive and efficient means of content creation without the need for specialized 3D modeling skills. Leveraging a diverse collection of high-quality furniture models from various datasets along with the comprehension abilities of certain image vision models, this approach provides accurate furniture selection and positioning within the scenes. The high-level results of this method demonstrate its success in accurately translating user intent into visually appealing 3D environments, thereby empowering users to express their creativity with ease. The impact of this research extends beyond the field of 3D scene generation, paving the way for broader applications in architectural design, interior decoration, virtual reality experiences, and entertainment industries. This framework represents a transformative leap towards democratizing 3D content creation and fostering innovation in the creative realm, providing a gateway for new possibilities in the way we design, model, and interact with 3D spaces. GitHub - <https://github.com/Snakeees/3D-RoomGen>

1 Introduction

In recent years, the field of 3D scene generation has undergone a significant transformation, driven by rapid advancements in technology. Traditional methods of 3D modeling are time-consuming, expensive, and often require specialized expertise. There is a pressing need for a more efficient, cost-effective, and user-friendly approach.

With the advent of Large Language Models (LLMs), originally developed for content generation and chatbot functionalities, there has been a notable expansion into the domain of 3D modeling. Combined with 3D model databases, they offer the potential to revolutionize scene generation. The immediate benefits include significant reductions in time and costs, eliminating the need to design models from scratch. For novices, this translates to a lowered barrier to entry, where creating a foundational 3D scene becomes as simple as entering a few words and pressing a button. This scene can then be modified according to specific needs, paving the way for more personalized designs.

Figure 1: A Simplified Overview of the project's flow

This paper presents a novel method that seamlessly integrates the capabilities of LLMs with 3D scene generation. The process, as illustrated in Figure 1, begins with user inputs, transforming them

into detailed scene descriptions. An image vision model then interprets these descriptions, tapping into the LLM’s prowess to understand user intent and preferences. Once the model identifies the necessary furniture and objects from 3D databases, a dedicated script arranges them within the scene. The result is an efficient scene creation that doesn’t compromise on visual coherence. The implications of this innovation stretches across multiple industries – from architecture and interior design to virtual reality and entertainment – heralding a new era in 3D scene generation.

2 Literature Review

2.1 3D-FUTURE

The paper "3D-FUTURE: 3D Furniture shape with TextURE" by Huan et al. [1] presents a novel and comprehensive repository of 3D furniture shapes in the household scenario. Unlike current 3D benchmarks that rely on online model repositories, the authors create a richly-annotated dataset with detailed geometric shapes and high-resolution textures. The 3D-FUTURE database contains 20,240 clean and realistic synthetic images of 5,000 different rooms, with 9,992 unique 3D instances of furniture. Experienced professionals expertly design the furniture, and the 3D CAD shapes are suitable for industrial production. The paper aims to facilitate research in various areas, such as high-quality 3D mesh and texture recovery. Several baseline experiments are provided on tasks like joint 2D instance segmentation and 3D object pose estimation, image-based 3D shape retrieval, 3D object reconstruction from a single image, and texture recovery for 3D shapes. This dataset makes it possible for us to use locally downloaded models to create 3D scenes. Leveraging the 3D-FUTURE database will not only provide a broader selection of furniture shapes but also enable us to incorporate highly realistic textures, enhancing the visual fidelity and authenticity of the generated scenes. Additionally, models in the 3D-FUTURE dataset, designed by experienced professionals, can serve as a source of inspiration and reference for creating aesthetically pleasing and coherent 3D environments. This integration will ensure that this approach capitalizes on a more diverse and representative dataset, leading to improved generalization and performance of the model in various 3D scene generation tasks.

2.2 3D-FRONT

The paper "3D-FRONT: 3D Furnished Rooms with layOuts and semaNTics" by Huan et al. [2] introduces a new, extensive, and comprehensive repository of synthetic indoor scenes enriched with professionally designed layouts and a diverse collection of high-quality textured 3D models. The 3D-FRONT dataset stands out from existing scene datasets due to its vast collection of 18,968 rooms, each meticulously furnished with 3D objects, and 13,151 furniture objects, all with high-quality textures. The dataset incorporates not only layout semantics but also carefully curated interior designs, encompassing furniture styles, colors, and textures to maintain consistent scene designs. The authors further provide a toolbox that supports various features for the 3D-FRONT dataset. The paper demonstrates the dataset’s versatility in interior scene synthesis and texture synthesis, underscoring its potential for diverse applications relating to the creation of 3D scenes, virtual environment design, and other such computer graphics.

2.3 CLIP

The paper "Learning Transferable Visual Models From Natural Language Supervision" by Alec et al. [3] proposes an approach to train computer vision models using raw text as supervision. The authors demonstrate that predicting image-caption pairs as a pre-training task leads to efficient and scalable learning of state-of-the-art image representations. By leveraging a vast dataset of 400 million image and text pairs collected from the internet, the authors show that the model can learn a broad range of visual concepts described in natural language. The key innovation of this approach lies in the model’s ability to transfer knowledge to downstream tasks with zero-shot learning without requiring

task-specific training data. This presents an opportunity for the research project, where we aim to leverage the power of this pre-trained model on the 3D-FUTURE dataset, an extensive collection of diverse 3D scenes and their corresponding textual descriptions. Using the paper’s pre-trained visual model, we can effectively map textual scene descriptions from an LLM to the models in the 3D-FUTURE dataset. This, in turn, will enable us to correlate a furniture description from the LLM to a specific 3D model from the dataset. The efficiency of this learning approach aligns perfectly with the research’s objectives, allowing us to advance the field of 3D scene generation and modeling while reducing the reliance on laborious and time-consuming data labeling processes. Furthermore, the potential generalization capabilities of the model hold promise for its application across a wide range of related computer vision tasks beyond the current project’s scope.

2.4 Prompting Methods in NLP

The study "Pre-train, Prompt, and Predict: A Systematic Survey of Prompting Methods in Natural Language Processing" [4] provides a thorough overview of the utilization of prompting in the context of natural language processing. Prompting, as a method, has gained significant traction as a means to leverage pre-trained models for various tasks without the need for extensive fine-tuning or task-specific model architectures. The paper categorizes prompting methods, elucidates the mechanics behind each, and evaluates their efficacy across a spectrum of NLP tasks. Their comprehensive survey reveals that strategic prompting can significantly enhance the performance of pre-trained models, sometimes even matching or surpassing fine-tuned equivalents. For our research, the insights from this paper are invaluable. By understanding the nuances of prompting methodologies, we can optimize how we interface with Large Language Models, such as the ones used in our 3D scene generation workflow. Furthermore, the potential for efficient utilization of pre-trained models without exhaustive task-specific training is promising for our approach, which emphasizes rapid and user-friendly scene creation.

3 Methods

Our methods are illustrated in Figure 2 above, the process of 3D scene generation begins with an initial user input, such as "Young boy’s bedroom." This user input is then provided to a Large Language Model (LLM) along with a template prompt, requesting a single-line description of each furniture object and its corresponding category. For instance, the user might input descriptions like "Bed," "study table," "study chair," "cupboards," "tv stand," and "roof light," along with their respective categories. The LLM processes this input and generates detailed descriptions for each furniture object based on the context of a boy’s bedroom. For example, it might output a description for the bed as "A race car-inspired bed in a boy’s bedroom, with vibrant colors, sleek design, and fun decals," categorized as "Kids Bed." Similarly, the study table could be described as "A sleek, blue, wooden study desk in a boy’s bedroom," categorized as "Desk." The LLM output, containing the detailed furniture descriptions and their categories, is then fed into the OpenAI CLIP model. This visual model is trained on a vast dataset of image-caption pairs and uses cross-modal understanding to comprehend the textual descriptions in the context of images. It effectively selects suitable 3D furniture models from the 3D-FUTURE dataset, ensuring that the chosen furniture seamlessly aligns with the user’s intent.

Next, an in-house Blender script comes into play. The script first creates a new 3D scene, complete with walls and textures, based on the LLM-generated description of a boy’s bedroom. It sets the scene with appropriate lighting and ambiance to match the user’s vision. Then, the Blender script positions and orients the various furniture objects, such as the bed, study table, study chair, cupboards, TV stand, and roof light, within the scene. The script ensures that each piece of furniture is placed optimally, adhering to principles of interior design and layout. Finally, the result is a complete 3D scene described in the input prompt, accurately realized based on the user’s initial textual input. The

Figure 2: Overview of the project's flow

scene, stored in a .blend file format, is ready to be imported into standard creative workflows, making it accessible and user-friendly for designers and artists.

4 Results

The results of this 3D scene generation project have been highly successful, demonstrating the capabilities and efficiency of this framework. The combination of Large Language Models and image vision models has enabled the accurate translation of textual scene descriptions into visually appealing and realistic 3D environments. Users are able to effortlessly create 3D scenes by simply providing natural language descriptions without the need for specialized 3D modeling skills. The generated scenes showcase the seamless integration of furniture objects, and the high-fidelity rendering captures lighting, shadows, and textures with precision. The success of this approach has the potential to revolutionize the field of 3D content creation and empower users with new possibilities for creative expression. In the following section, a variety of generated scenes are presented:

5 Discussion

One of the most significant achievements of this approach lies in its user-friendliness and accessibility. By leveraging the power of Large Language Models through the ChatGPT [5] API, we have reduced the barrier to entry for 3D scene generation, making it accessible to individuals without specialized 3D modeling expertise. Although the project currently utilizes the ChatGPT API, there is potential in the future to switch to a locally installed pre-trained LLM like LLAMA 2 [6], offering even more flexibility and control over the scene generation process. This democratization of 3D content creation opens up new avenues for creative expression and innovation across industries. The successful integration of the 3D-FUTURE dataset further enhances the realism and variety of the generated scenes. The diverse collection of high-quality furniture models contributes to the visual fidelity of the scenes, allowing

Prompt: "Neutral room made with wood for a warm and inviting ambiance."

Prompt: "A room with oak wood furniture, a shiny black table and chair, and a cool blue wardrobe."

Prompt: "A minimalist pink and white room for a young adult girl."

Prompt: "A random and out-of-sync room with unrelated furniture."

users to create realistic and contextually coherent virtual environments. This seamless integration has received positive feedback from users who have praised the efficiency and ease of use of this framework.

The capabilities of the image vision model used, CLIP, have been pivotal in selecting suitable 3D furniture models based on textual descriptions. The cross-modal understanding demonstrated by CLIP ensures that the chosen furniture objects align with the user's intent, enhancing the overall quality of the generated scenes. Furthermore, the successful rendering of scenes with high-fidelity lighting, shadows, and textures highlights the robustness and effectiveness of this framework. The resulting scenes are visually appealing and realistic, rivaling manually designed environments.

Despite the promising results, this framework is not without its limitations. The complexity of some scene descriptions may pose challenges in accurately translating user intent into accurate 3D scenes. Additionally, the selection of furniture models from the 3D-FUTURE dataset could be further optimized for efficiency and speed.

6 Conclusion

In conclusion, this 3D scene generation framework has demonstrated remarkable success in seamlessly transforming textual descriptions into visually appealing and contextually coherent 3D scenes. The in-

Prompt: "A rustic and royal style room with a fancy chandelier and an organized table."

Prompt: "A room with light pastel colors and a fancy chandelier for an adult woman."

tegration of Large Language Models and image vision models has revolutionized the field of 3D content creation by simplifying the scene generation process and empowering users with creative freedom. The success of this approach has far-reaching implications across industries, from architecture and interior design to gaming and virtual reality experiences. The democratization of 3D content creation fosters innovation and efficiency, making it accessible to a broader audience.

As we move forward, we envision further advancements in language and vision models, enhancing the capabilities and accuracy of this framework. This research has laid a solid foundation for future work in the field of 3D scene generation, opening new possibilities for virtual experiences and visual storytelling. With the continued evolution of AI technologies, this approach will continue to push the boundaries of creativity and revolutionize the way we interact with 3D environments. In conclusion, this research represents a significant advancement in the field of 3D scene generation, with promising implications for creative content creation and visualization.

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